

PROBLEM TEACHING METHODS IN GEOGRAPHY

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Abstract: The article talks about the problems and solutions of the problem-based teaching methodology in the teaching of geography, the main problems of natural geographical problems that have affected society throughout the history of mankind.

Keyword: Science of geography, methodology, problem, natural geography.

The method of problem-based teaching in geography is one of the advanced teaching methods, because it makes students think? forces them to search, as a result of which their knowledge deepens and the skills of posing and solving various problems are formed. Problems in geography and their use in the educational process. Since the science of geography consists of natural and economic-social parts, all the problems of nature and society are embodied in it. These problems are formed and developed as a result of natural and economic-social processes and their interaction. One of the most important conditions for using these problems in the educational process is to divide them into groups according to their origin. These problems can be divided into the following groups: - natural geographical problems; - socio-economic geographical problems; - geocological problems; - educational and educational problems; Natural geographic problems have been and remain one of the main problems affecting society throughout human history. We can include the following in such problems: a) problems related to the characteristics of the Earth's crust (earthquakes, volcanoes, tectonic movements, etc.); b) problems related to the atmosphere and climate (strong winds, floods, lightning, hail, frostbite, drought, etc.); c) problems related to surface water (flooding, swamping, etc.); g) biological problems, that is, problems related to soil, flora and fauna; d) Problems related to the world ocean (ocean level rise, typhoon, tsunami). Problems (processes) related to the characteristics of the earth's crust cannot be known in advance, only by knowing their occurrence in advance, it is possible to take appropriate measures. For example, if it is possible to predict the occurrence of an earthquake or a volcano, the population in

these areas will be evacuated. As a result of tectonic movements, the gradual rise and fall of certain areas of the Earth's surface can be explained by the example of the Netherlands. As a result of the gradual subsidence of the Earth's crust, the territory of the Netherlands remains below sea level. As a result, there was a risk of flooding the territory of the Netherlands. To prevent this, a dam was built on the seashore, and its height is raised every year. Problems related to the atmosphere and climate have been of interest to mankind since ancient times. At present, the occurrence of certain atmospheric phenomena is predicted and measures are developed accordingly. For example, floods, frostbite, drought, storms, etc. Problems related to surface water are currently identified in advance and appropriate measures are developed. Such problems (processes) include the formation of floods and swamps. Biogeographical problems include soil erosion and the change or decline of flora and fauna. They mainly occur as a result of sudden changes in natural conditions. Problems related to the world's oceans remain one of the most important problems for countries located on the coasts and islands. As a result of the gradual warming of the Earth's climate, continental and mountain glaciers are melting and the level of the world ocean is rising, typhoons and tsunamis are causing great damage to the peoples living on the coasts and islands. For example, as a result of the tsunami that occurred in Indonesia in the winter of 2005, thousands of residents and vacationers died. Economic geographical problems are also among the main problems of people. For example, natural resources and their use; demographic and demographic problems; production deployment and development problems; problems of transport and international economic relations. Geoecological problems arise as a result of the interaction of nature and society, and we can divide them into the following groups: - problems of rational use of natural resources; - problems of nature protection; - problems of nature restoration; The problems of rational use of nature and natural resources are considered a common human problem facing all sciences at the present time. As a result of the improper use of nature, large areas of soil have become salinized, soil quality has decreased due to wind and water erosion, their productivity has decreased due to the intensive use of pastures, forest areas have decreased due to the improper use of plant resources. shrunk, with the development of hunting, many animals in the history of mankind have become completely extinct or are on the verge of complete extinction. In this regard, in order to protect nature and natural resources, reserves, national parks, biosphere reserves, and sanctuaries have been established all over the world. Red books of the world and individual countries have been published and are being made. At present, a lot of work is being done to restore natural complexes

damaged by man. Man-made landscapes created as a result of industrial production are being transformed into parks, forests, plantations and recreation areas. One of the main tasks of geography education is the wide use of the above problems in the process of developing problematic lesson technologies and their deeper inculcation in the minds of students. The development of problem-based educational technology will be very effective if the problems of Uzbekistan and Central Asia are used. For example, the problem of the island, the problem of diverting Siberian rivers to Central Asia, the problem of extensive agricultural development and soil salinization.

Problem statement method. It is called the method of problem statement, based on the teacher's explanation of the problem and ways to solve it. With the help of this method, teachers acquire skills about ways to solve natural geographical, economic geographical and geocological problems and methods of their justification. When using this method, attention is paid to the following: - the teacher raises a problem and shows an example of how to solve it, that is, he solves this problem himself during the presentation of the lesson topic; - students monitor the teacher's steps in solving this problem and acquire the skills of solving geographical problems during the lesson. During the solution of a certain problem, the teacher shows the ways of solving it, during the solution of the problem, the conflict of ideas arises, the students' ideas are attracted to the features of the development of ideas. During the description of the solution of the problem, the teacher shows an example of scientific knowledge and scientific thinking. The students watched and controlled the stages of solving the problem, the level of its scientific basis, and the development of ideas. In the lessons of natural geography, he can show an example of solving the following problems: The problem of the island and its surroundings, in which the teacher should scientifically justify the reasons for the construction of the Aral Sea and its consequences, as well as ways to solve the problem of the island; - atmospheric pollution and, in connection with it, the average temperature on the Earth's surface should regularly increase and reveal its consequences; - it is necessary to justify the cutting of forests and the change of natural conditions in connection with it; - When passing through the terrain of Uzbekistan, it is possible to show the example of solving the problems faced by the teacher. "Uzbekistan's terrain is a result of the interaction of internal and external forces." In this case, it will be revealed in the lesson report what forms of relief are formed by the interaction of internal and external forces and how they change under the influence of external forces; When discussing the topic of Uzbekistan's natural regions, it is possible to point out the problem and show ways to solve it. The natural conditions of Uzbekistan change

from west to east due to the increase in absolute altitude and climate change. In this, students' attention is drawn to the fact that the climate cools down as the altitude increases, and as a result, desert, hill, mountain and high mountain regions appeared in Uzbekistan. In economic and social geography lessons, problem lessons can be organized on the topics of natural resources, population geography, location of production forces, transport and international economic relations, creation of economic regions, geographical distribution of labor. The following problems can be studied in the classes of economic and social geography: - the power of any state depends on its level of development and natural resources. If the country is highly developed and has enough natural resources, the power of that country will be high, for example, Russia, China, USA, Great Britain, etc. States can be powerful even if they are highly developed but have few natural resources and high intellectual (human) resources, for example, Japan; - dependence of the location of production forces on natural conditions and natural resources, as well as labor forces; - that population migration depends on economic and political conditions; - that the level of industrial development depends on the level of use of the results of the scientific and technical revolution; - the development of any country depends on the development of its international specialized field. Geocological problems are encountered in almost any subject in geography classes. Therefore, geography is one of the main subjects that provide environmental education and training to students and the general public. An example of how to solve geocological problems can be shown: - If the Aral Sea dries up completely, what geographical changes will occur around the island. In solving these problems, the teacher should first reveal its natural geographical consequences, then economic geographical consequences, and finally geocological consequences. After that, it is necessary to justify the measures to prevent the drying up of the Aral Sea; - improper location of industrial enterprises and its geocological consequences. An example of these problems is the aluminum plant in Tajikistan. The causes of the unpleasant environmental processes that occurred in southern Uzbekistan due to the construction and operation of this plant should be revealed; - the development of cotton monopolies in Uzbekistan during the former union and its environmental consequences should be revealed by the teacher as a problem statement; - climate change and its impact on natural conditions can also be revealed in the process of problem statement.

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